

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 125

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 135

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 135:1 ¹Praise ²the LORD! Praise the name of the LORD; Praise <i>Him</i>, O ^bservants of the LORD, ² You who stand in the house of the LORD, In the ^acourts of the house of our God! ³ ¹Praise ²the LORD, for ^athe LORD is good; ^bSing praises to His name, ^afor it is lovely. ⁴ For ¹the LORD has ^achosen Jacob for Himself, Israel for His ^{2b}own possession.</p> <p>Psa. 135:5 For I know that ^athe LORD is great And that our Lord is ^babove all gods. ⁶ ^aWhatever the LORD pleases, He does, In heaven and in earth, in the seas and in all deeps. ⁷ ¹He ^acauses the ²vapors to ascend from the ends of the earth; Who ^bmakes lightnings for the rain, Who ^abrings forth the wind from His treasuries.</p> <p>Psa. 135:8 ¹He ^asmote the firstborn of Egypt, ²Both of man and beast.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 135:1</p> <p>יְהוָה הַלְלוּ יְהוָה הַלְלוּ אֶת־שְׁמֵי יְהוָה הַלְלוּ עַבְדֵי יְהוָה : ² שְׁעֵמֻדִים בְּבֵית יְהוָה בְּחַצְרוֹת בַּיִת אֱלֹהֵינוּ : ³ הַלְלוּ־יְהוָה כִּי־טוֹב יְהוָה וּמְרוֹ לְשִׁמּוֹ כִּי נְעִים : ⁴ כִּי־יֵעֲקֹב בְּתָר לוֹ יְהוָה אֲשֶׁר־אֵל לְסִגְלָתוֹ : ⁵ כִּי אֲנִי יַדְעֹתִי כִּי־גִדּוֹל יְהוָה וְאֲדֹנָינוּ מִכָּל־אֱלֹהִים : ⁶ כָּל אֲשֶׁר־חָפֵץ יְהוָה עָשָׂה בַשָּׁמַיִם וּבָאָרֶץ בַּיָּמִים וְכָל־תְּהוֹמוֹת : ⁷ מִעֲלֵה נְשָׁאִים מִקְצֵה הָאָרֶץ בְּרָקִים לְמַטֵּר עָשָׂה מוֹצֵא־רֹחַ מֵאוֹצְרוֹתָיו : ⁸ שִׁהַכָּה בְּכוֹרֵי מִצְרַיִם מֵאָדָם עַד־בְּהֵמָה : ⁹ שָׁלַח אֲתוֹת וּמִפְתִּים בְּתוֹכָכִי מִצְרַיִם בְּפִרְעֹה וּבְכָל־עַבְדָּיו : ¹⁰ שִׁהַכָּה גּוֹיִם רַבִּים וְהִרְג מַלְכִים עֲצוּמִים : ¹¹ לְסִיחוֹן אֶמְלֹךְ הָאֲמֹרִי וְלַעֲזוּג מֶלֶךְ הַבְּשָׁן וְלִכְלֹל מִמְּלָכוֹת כְּנָעַן : ¹² וְנָתַן אֶרְצָם נַחֲלָה נַחֲלָה לְיִשְׂרָאֵל עַמּוֹ : ¹³ יְהוָה שִׁמְךָ לְעוֹלָם יְהוָה זְכָרְךָ לְדוֹר־וָדוֹר : ¹⁴ כִּי־יִדְּיוּ יְהוָה עַמּוֹ וְעַל־עַבְדָּיו יִתְנַחֵם : ¹⁵ עַצְבֵי הַגּוֹיִם כִּסֹּף וְזָהַב מִעֲשֵׂה יְדֵי אָדָם : ¹⁶ פֶּה־לָהֶם וְלֹא</p>

⁹ ¹He sent ^asigns and wonders into
your midst, O Egypt,
Upon ^bPharaoh and all his
servants.
¹⁰ ^{1a}He ^bsmote many nations
And slew mighty kings,
¹¹ ^aSihon, king of the Amorites,
And ^bOg, king of Bashan,
And ^call the kingdoms of Canaan;
¹² And He ^agave their land as a
heritage,
A heritage to Israel His people.
¹³ Your ^aname, O LORD, is
everlasting,
Your ¹remembrance, O LORD,
²throughout all generations.
¹⁴ For the LORD will ^ajudge His
people
And ^bwill have compassion on His
servants.
¹⁵ The ^aidols of the nations are *but*
silver and gold,
The work of man's hands.
¹⁶ They have mouths, but they do
not speak;
They have eyes, but they do not
see;
¹⁷ They have ears, but they do not
hear,
Nor is there any breath at all in
their mouths.
¹⁸ Those who make them will be like
them,
Yes, everyone who trusts in them.

Psa. 135:19 O house of ^aIsrael,
bless the LORD;
O house of Aaron, bless the
LORD;
²⁰ O house of Levi, bless the
LORD;

¹⁷ יִדְבְּרוּ עֵינַיִם לָהֶם וְלֹא יֵרְאוּ :
אֲזַנַּיִם לָהֶם וְלֹא יִשְׁמְעוּ אֶת אֲזַיִן
יִשְׁרוּת בְּפִיהֶם : ¹⁸ כַּמֹּזְהֵם יִהְיוּ
עֹשֵׂיהֶם כֹּל אֲשֶׁר-בִּטְטָה בָּהֶם : ¹⁹
בֵּית יִשְׂרָאֵל בְּרַכּוּ אֶת-יְהוָה בֵּית
אַהֲרֹן בְּרַכּוּ אֶת-יְהוָה : ²⁰ בֵּית
הַלְוִי בְרַכּוּ אֶת-יְהוָה יֵרְאֵי יְהוָה
בְּרַכּוּ אֶת-יְהוָה : ²¹ בְּרוּךְ יְהוָה |
מִצִּיּוֹן שֹׁכֵן יְרוּשָׁלַם הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה :

<p>You ^awho ¹revere the LORD, bless the LORD. ²¹ Blessed be the LORD ^afrom Zion, Who ^bdwells in Jerusalem. ¹Praise ²the LORD!</p>	
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References

Psalm 135:1

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aPs 113:1

^bPs 134:1

Psalm 135:2

^aPs 92:13; 116:19

Psalm 135:3

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aPs 100:5; 119:68

^bPs 68:4

^cPs 147:1

Psalm 135:4

¹Heb *YAH*

²Or *special treasure*

^aDeut 7:6; 10:15; Ps 105:6

^bEx 19:5; Mal 3:17; Titus 2:14; 1 Pet 2:9

Psalm 135:5

^aPs 48:1; 95:3; 145:3

^bPs 97:9

Psalm 135:6

^aPs 115:3

Psalm 135:7

¹Lit *The one who*

²I.e. clouds

^aJer 10:13; 51:16

^bJob 28:25, 26; 38:25, 26; Zech 10:1

Psalm 135:8

¹Lit *The one who*

²Lit *From man to beast*

^aEx 12:12; Ps 78:51; 105:36

Psalm 135:9

¹Lit *The one who*

^aEx 7:10; Deut 6:22; Ps 78:43

^bPs 136:15

Psalm 135:10

¹Lit *The one who*

^aNum 21:24; Ps 135:10-12; 136:17-21

^bPs 44:2

Psalm 135:11

^aNum 21:21-26; Deut 29:7

^bNum 21:33-35

Josh 12:7-24

Psalm 135:12

^aDeut 29:8; Ps 78:55; 136:21, 22

Psalm 135:13

¹Or *memorial*

²Lit *to*

^aEx 3:15; Ps 102:12

Psalm 135:14

^aDeut 32:36; Ps 50:4

^bPs 90:13; 106:46

Psalm 135:15

^aPs 115:4-8; 135:15-18

Psalm 135:19

^aPs 115:9

Psalm 135:20

¹Lit *fear*

^aPs 118:4

Psalm 135:21

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aPs 128:5; 134:3

^bPs 132:14

Targum

Psa. 135:1 Hallelujah! Praise the name of the LORD, praise, O servants of the LORD!
² Who stand in the sanctuary of the LORD, in the courts of the house of our God. ³
Hallelujah! For the LORD is good; sing to his name, for it is pleasant. ⁴ For the house
of Jacob the LORD chose for himself, Israel, for his beloved. ⁵ For I know, for great is
the LORD, and our master over all gods. ⁶ All that the LORD desires, he has done in
heaven and on earth, in the seas and all the deeps. ⁷ Who brings up clouds from the
ends of the earth; he made lightning for the fall of rain, he who brings forth the storm
from his storehouses. ⁸ Who slew the firstborn of Egypt, from man to beast. ⁹ He sent
signs and wonders into your midst, O Egypt, against Pharaoh and all his servants. ¹⁰
Who smote many Gentiles and slew mighty kings. ¹¹ Namely, Sihon the Amorite king,
and Og, the king of Mathnan, and all the kingdoms of Canaan. ¹² And gave their land
as an inheritance, an inheritance for Israel his people. ¹³ O LORD, your name is forever;
O LORD, your memorial is for all generations. ¹⁴ For the LORD by his word will judge
the case of his people, and will turn in his compassion to all his righteous servants. ¹⁵
The idols of the Gentiles are silver and gold, the work of the hands of a son of man. ¹⁶
They have a mouth, but do not speak; eyes they have, but do not see. ¹⁷ They have ears,
but do not hear; nostrils, but there is no breath of life in their mouth. ¹⁸ Their makers
will be like them, all who put their trust in them. ¹⁹ house of Israel, bless the LORD!
House of Aaron, bless the LORD! ²⁰ House of Levites, bless the LORD! You who fear
the LORD, bless the LORD! ²¹ Blessed is the LORD from Zion, who has made his
presence abide in Jerusalem. Hallelujah!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The Psalmist looks forward to the Messianic era when there will be an unprecedented outpouring of praise to the LORD. Humanity will come to understand that the LORD was in all events.

Notes on this Psalm

This Psalm is a collection of hallelujahs to the LORD for His presence throughout history. Sometimes it is difficult to see the LORD at work in humanity's history because Evil Inclination also exists. The LORD would not cause some of the horror to occur that history talks about. Evil inclination caused the horrors of history. In the days of the Psalmist, it was believed that the LORD caused everything to occur. In modern days scholars have determined that Evil inclination has a lot of influence. The LORD gave humanity freewill. This means that a person can follow Evil Inclination, or the LORD. Those persons who follow the LORD need to show the people who follow Evil Inclination that it is not in their best interest. Evil people need to shed the Klippot and return to the LORD.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

